

PL-50 polyflex gelvanometer. The capillary characteristics were: $m=2.18 \text{ mg s}^{-1}$ and $t=3.0 \text{ s}$ at 40.0 cm (39.98 cm) effective height of mercury¹. The study was carried out at 25 and 35°.

Results and Discussions

Pr^{III} gives a well-defined three-electron reversible reduction wave in KCl and gelatin². The nature of waves of metal and its complexes were reversible and diffusion-controlled as revealed from the straight lines plots of $\log i/(i_a-i)$ vs $E_{d,e}$ and i_d vs \sqrt{h} respectively. Lingane's method³ confirmed the formation of 1 : 1 complexes of Pr^{III} with all the three ligands at 25 and 35°. The values of stability constants are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF Pr^{III} COMPLEXES OF THE LIGANDS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

pH = 2.40 ± 0.1, $\mu = 1.0 \text{ M}$ (KCl), $E_{1/2} = 1.81 \text{ V}$ vs S.C.E.

Ligand	log β	
	25°	35°
Glycine	4.40	3.70
L-Asparagine	3.50	3.10
L-Glutamine	3.45	2.60

The trend of stabilities of complexes is L-glutamine < L-asparagine < glycine. As the size of amino acid increases the stability of complexes decreases⁴. The lesser stability of L-glutamine than L-asparagine complexes is due to the greater steric hindrance in the former. The higher stability of glycine complexes is well-known⁵.

Acknowledgement

Authors thank Dr. S. P. Banerjee, Professor and Head, Department of Chemistry and Dean of Faculty of Science, Dr. H. S. Gour University, Sagar, for facilities and M. P. University Grants Commission, Bhopal, to provide a Fellowship to one of the authors (K.N.).

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Studies on Mixed Ligand Complexes of Dioxouranium with Salicyl Hydroxamic Acid

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Manuscript received 31 March 1989, revised 9 April 1990,
accepted 11 May 1990

A resume on salicylhydroxamic acid (SHA) enlightens its analytical use where its coordinating behaviour is found to be limited to the formation of 1 : 2 complexes with various oxometal ions¹. The present communication deals with the preparation and characterisation of some mixed chelates of dioxouranium(VI) with SHA of the type, $(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{UO}_2\text{L}_2\text{X}_2]$, $n\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{NH}_4[\text{UO}_2\text{L}_2\text{Y}, \text{H}_2\text{O}]$, $n\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $[\text{UO}_2\text{L}_2\text{B}]$, $n\text{H}_2\text{O}$, where L is the deprotonated mono-anion of SHA, $\text{X} = 1/2\text{CO}_3^{2-}$, $1/2\text{SO}_4^{2-}$, $1/2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$, CH_3COO^- , NO_3^- , Cl^- ; $\text{Y} = \text{Br}^-$, I^- ; $\text{B} = 1,10\text{-phenanthroline (Phen)}$, $2,2\text{'-bipyridyl (bipy)}$, $\text{CO}(\text{NH}_2)_2$; and $n = 0-3$.

Experimental

SHA was prepared by the reported method². All other reagents were of A.R. grade.

Preparation of $(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{UO}_2(\text{L})_2\text{X}_2], n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{NH}_4[\text{UO}_2\text{L}_2\text{Y}, \text{H}_2\text{O}], n\text{H}_2\text{O}$: To an aqueous solution of uranyl nitrate hexahydrate (~0.002 mol) the ammonium salt (0.005 mol) containing X or Y anion was added with constant stirring to obtain a clear solution. A solution of SHA (0.006–0.008 mol) in either 2 : 1 acetone-water or in acetone was added to it with constant stirring. The precipitate appeared either immediately or on stirring for a long time. The resulting yellowish orange to reddish brown crystals were filtered, washed with warm water, ethanol or acetone and finally dried in a vacuum desiccator over concentrated H_2SO_4 (yield 60–80%).

Preparation of $[\text{UO}_2\text{L}_2\text{B}], n\text{H}_2\text{O}$: Uranyl nitrate hexahydrate (0.002 mol) in ethanol or methanol was mixed with phen/bipy (B; 0.006 mol) in the same solvent. To the resulting suspension SHA (0.006 mol) in 1 : 1 acetone-water was added with constant stirring to obtain a red solution. A reddish brown/yellowish red precipitate separated on long stirring was dried as before (50–70%).

The estimation of uranium, nitrogen, halogens and other physicochemical measurements were done according to the procedure described in our previous work³.

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NOTES

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd *	Analysis % : Found/Calcd)			% Loss (100°) Found/(Calcd)	ΔM Ω^{-1} cm ² mol ⁻¹
	U	N	Anion		
(NH ₄) ₂ [UO ₂ L ₂ CO ₃] 2H ₂ O	32 79 (33 71)	—	—	5.19 (5 09)	63 4
(NH ₄) ₂ [UO ₂ L ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂] H ₂ O	32 22 (31 90)	3 60 (3 75)	—	2 69 (2 41)	57 3
(NH ₄) ₂ [UO ₂ L ₂ C ₂ O ₄] 3H ₂ O	31 43 (31 64)	3 50 (3 45)	—	7 09 (7 18)	61 6
(NH ₄) ₂ [UO ₂ L ₂ SO ₄] 2H ₂ O	32 24 (32 08)	—	—	—	50 2
(NH ₄) ₂ [UO ₂ L ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]·H ₂ O	31 64 (31 64)	—	—	2 46 (2 39)	45 4
(NH ₄) ₂ [UO ₂ L ₂ Cl ₂] 2H ₂ O	32 80 (33 19)	—	9 42 (9 90)	5 45 (5 02)	43 7
NH ₄ [UO ₂ L ₂ Br H ₂ O] H ₂ O	33 25 (33 61)	—	10 45 (11 29)	—	55 4
NH ₄ [UO ₂ L ₂ I H ₂ O] H ₂ O	31 65 (31 52)	—	15 90 (16 82)	2 53 (2 38)	40 2
[UO ₂ L ₂ (phen)]	31 49 (31 56)	—	—	—	17 4
[UO ₂ L ₂ (bipy)]	32 16 (32 60)	—	—	—	13 8
[UO ₂ L ₂ ·2CO(NH ₂) ₂] 2H ₂ O	32 51 (32 60)	3 1 (3 28)	—	—	14 7

*L=C₇H₆O₂N

Results and Discussion

Molar conductance values of the complexes (Table 1) showed that with the exception of the bipy, phen and urea complexes, the others were electrolytes. Conductance values were lower than those of 2 : 1 or 1 : 1 electrolytes⁴ suggesting partial ionisation of the complexes in DMF solvent.

The weight-loss at $\leq 110^\circ$ corresponds to the elimination of lattice water. All the compounds decomposed between 110° and 240° with a sharp mass loss accountable for the expulsion of both the SHA moiety at a time. The decomposition temperatures gave the following order of thermal stability of the complexes : sulphato < *o*-phen < urea < bromo=bipy < oxalato < chloro < carbonato < iodo < nitrate < acetato. At 600° the residue had a constant weight due to U₃O₈.

The solution spectra of all the complexes exhibited a band at 360–380 nm due to charge transfer. A low intensity band at ~ 450 nm both in solution and solid spectra suggests⁵ a transition due to $^1\Sigma_g^+ \rightarrow ^3\Pi_u$. The similarity in the solid state and solution spectra indicates the stability of the complexes in DMF.

A broad ir band (~ 3180 cm⁻¹) in the complexes indicates the presence of hydroxamic OH group⁶ which is further established by the presence of δ_{NOH} in all the complexes³. Phenolic hydroxyl group deprotonates² to bind the central metal atom and thus cannot result O–H bond as in free ligand. A band at 3280 cm⁻¹ is assigned⁷ to ν_{NH} . A strong $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ band at 1630 cm⁻¹ in the free ligand was lowered by ~ 40 cm⁻¹ in all the complexes indicating the coordination through keto group¹. The band

around 1360 cm⁻¹ was assigned to $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$. ν_{asy} (UO₂²⁺) band was observed in all the complexes in the region 900 – 930 cm⁻¹ as a bifurcated band. The $\delta_{\text{O=O}}$ band appeared at 250 – 260 cm⁻¹ and the absence of ν_{sym} (UO₂) suggests the linearity of the uranyl entity. The 1775 and 1520 cm⁻¹ bands in the carbonato complex indicates the presence of coordinated carbonato group. The $\nu_{\text{U-O}}$ band at 450 cm⁻¹ suggests the bidentate nature of the carbonato group⁸. The ν_{as} and ν_3 band in the acetato complex at 1520 and 1400 cm⁻¹ respectively, indicates the unidentate non-bridging nature of acetate group⁹. The bands at 660 and 685 cm⁻¹ are due to $\nu_{\text{O-C-O}}$ and $\delta_{\text{U-O}}$ respectively. The separation of band position of ~ 300 cm⁻¹ between $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO})$ and $\nu_3(\text{COO})$ in the oxalato complex suggests bidentate nature of oxalate ion¹⁰. The bands at 740 and 560 cm⁻¹ are attributed to $\delta_{\text{O-C-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{U-O}}$ respectively⁸. The splitting of ν_3 (1090 , 1060 , 1030 cm⁻¹) and ν_4 (660 , 635 , 600 cm⁻¹) in the sulphato complex indicate the bidentate nature of the sulphate group¹¹. The narrow energy different between ν_1 and ν_4 bands in the nitrate complex indicates the unidentate nature of nitrate group¹². The $\nu_{\text{U-Cl}}$ and $\nu_{\text{U-I}}$ bands were observed at 280 cm⁻¹ while the $\nu_{\text{U-Br}}$ band at 285 cm⁻¹ for the halo complexes¹³. In 1,10-phenanthroline and 2,2'-bipyridyl complexes, the $\nu_{\text{U-N}}$ bands¹⁴ were observed at 275 cm⁻¹. The 660 and 410 cm⁻¹ bands with UO₂(L)₂bipy complex ensured chelation¹⁵ by the bipy ligand.

The force constants calculated¹⁶ by using mean $\bar{\nu}_3$ values gave U–O distance of 1.73 Å which are in good agreement with the available data of dioxouranium(VI) complexes.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (C.R.D.) is grateful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for the award of a Teacher Fellowship.

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Studies on some Oxozirconium(IV) and Dioxouranium(VI) Schiff Base Complexes

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Manuscript received 26 July 1989, revised 19 February 1990,
accepted 11 May 1990

MANY Schiff base complexes of transition metals using aldehydes and ketones have been reported from this laboratory¹. The present communication deals with the synthesis and characterisation of some Schiff base complexes of oxozirconium(IV) and dioxouranium(VI) using analytical, conductance, ir and ¹H nmr spectral studies.

Experimental

The complexes were prepared using the following two steps. (a) A mixture of furan-2-aldehyde (0.01

mol, 1.66 ml) in methanol (25 ml), glacial acetic acid (0.5 ml) and aniline (0.01 mol, 1.82 ml) or ethylene diamine (0.005 mol, 1.32 ml) was refluxed for 10–12 h. When the colour of solution changed from red to brown, the solvent was distilled off and the ligands were crystallised out from the light brown fraction after running the solution over tlc plates and analysed. (b) A mixture of appropriate oxometal chloride or acetate (0.01 mol) and ligand L₁ (0.02 mol, 3.42 g) or L₂ (0.01 mol, 2.16 g) was refluxed for 5 h. The solid complexes were crystallised using petroleum ether, purified by running over tlc plates, dried and analysed (Table 1).

The thiocyanate and perchlorate complexes were prepared by adding ammonium thiocyanate/potassium perchlorate to the solution of oxometal chlorides and ligand L₁ or L₂ in dry methanol (50 ml) and refluxing the mixture for 5 h. After filtering ammonium/potassium chloride, the complexes were crystallised out as in the previous case (Table 1).

The complexes were characterised on the basis of elemental analysis, molar conductance, ir and ¹H nmr spectral studies. The molar conductances were measured in MeOH and DMSO on a Toshniwal conductivity bridge. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer (90 MHz).

Results and Discussion

The theoretical condensation reactions show that ligand L₁ is bi- and L₂ is tetradentate in nature and hence their complexes should possess 1 : 2 and 1 : 1 stoichiometry respectively, which are confirmed by analytical data. The conductance of all complexes are in the usual range of 1 : 2 electrolytes (40–60 in DMSO, 160–220 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ in MeOH) and hence these are formulated as [ZrO(L₁)₂ or (L₂)]₂X₂ and [UO₂(L₁)₂ or (L₂)]₂X₂, where X = Cl⁻, ClO₄⁻, SCN⁻ and CH₃COO⁻.

The ir spectra of free ligands reveal bands at 1 600, 1 540, 1 500 and 1 450 cm⁻¹ due to aromatic and heterocyclic ring vibrations and these show a positive shift in case of the complexes². A sharp band at 1 610 cm⁻¹ (azomethine stretch) of the free ligand shifts to 1 590 cm⁻¹ in case of the complexes indicating the coordination through its nitrogen atom³.

The ν_{O-U=O} and ν_{Zr=O} bands are observed at 910 ± 5 and 970 ± 5 cm⁻¹ respectively⁴. Other bands were observed at 511 (ionic chloride)⁵, 2 050, 750, 485 (uncoordinated thiocyanate)⁶, 1 085, 620 (uncoordinated perchlorate)⁷ and 2 936, 1 414, 930, 675 cm⁻¹ (uncoordinated acetate ion)⁸. These spectra are in accordance with the conductance data of the complexes.

In the ¹H nmr spectra of ligand L₁, the CH protons appear as singlet at δ 2.05 (2H) whereas the heterocyclic and the phenyl ring protons merge